

Five Principles and Recommendations towards a More Open European Labour Market for Researchers

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1. Researchers should be provided with central and easy access to all vacancies that fit their profile.

Appropriate legal measures should be taken to ensure that at least all publicly funded researcher's positions are openly advertised at a central access point (EURAXESS job database).

2. Application procedures should be efficient and user-friendly and should avoid waste of time for researchers.

In particular, it has to be ensured that application documents can easily be reused.

3. Positions should be open for researchers regardless of their nationality.

The principle of non-discrimination should be put into practice by all employers in ERA countries and apply to all applicants regardless of their nationality.

4. Application procedures should be transparent and fair

Recruitment practice in European research institutions should follow the Principles of the “European Charter for Researchers and the Code of conduct for the recruitment of researchers” (Recruitment, Selection, Transparency, Judging merit, Variations in the chronological order of CVs, Recognition of mobility experience, Recognition of qualifications, Seniority, Postdoctoral appointments).

5. Timely information of candidates should be a matter of course

All candidates (both successful and sorted out) should be kept updated on the progress of the application procedure.

This recommendation has to be seen in context of other well-established policy with the aim to make the European Research Area more efficient and more attractive: **Recognition of doctoral candidates as Early Stage Researchers**, the necessity of **social security** provisions for all researchers including young researchers, **attractive career paths**, removing obstacles for mobility (**geographical as well as intersectoral mobility**), involvement of **young researchers in advisory and decision making bodies** and much more.